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Research Article

**PREVALENCE OF MENTAL ILLNESS PEOPLES IN
PAKISTAN**

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Abstract:

Background: Mental illness is related with the condition that not only affects the mental condition of person but show its affects on feelings and thoughts of general public. These situation impact deeply on the daily life of people and makes them unable to deal with even normal situation. There are various forms of mental illness such as anxiety disorder, depression and schizophrenia. The chances of disease are higher in developed countries as compared to developing countries people of developed countries have to deal with more problems and complex situations.

Objective: The study was conducted to find cause and prevalence of various types of mental illness with respect to gender, society, age, profession and qualification.

Methodology: A cross observation study was conducted for the people which were dealing with mental health concern. The data was collected of almost 100 patients including men and women of different age groups. Moreover, it was also accessed in the study that how awareness about mental illness leads to better health of person.

Results: The results showed that 46 out of 100 patients were professional while most of the patients were non-professional which determined that when people remained free and does not do any work than there are more chances of development of mental diseases. Furthermore, most of the people as 47 out of 100 were graduated, thus it is clear from study that young people are highly affected with mental related disorders. The most associated problem of mental illness is that people remain unaware of treatment methods such as results confirmed that 35 out of 100 patients were unaware of both counselling method and other medication treatment.

Conclusion: The prevalence of mental diseases especially depression and anxiety disorders are increasing day by day. Due to innovation in all products of regular use, the ease for human is increased but also leads to development of various new disease especially mental health problems. The cause of mental diseases is different for different people but the most common is change in culture, family problems and status issues.

Keyword: Mental illness post-traumatic stress disorder border line personality disorders obsessive compulsive disorder

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INTRODUCTION:

Mental illness is also known as mental health disorder that is a condition that affects the thoughts, feeling, behavior and thinking of people. There are various form of mental illness such as schizophrenia, anxiety disorder, depression, addictive behaviors, attention deficit hyperactivity disorder, bipolar disorder, borderline personality disorder, dissociative disorder, obsessive-compulsive disorder, post-traumatic stress disorder, psychosis and schizoaffective disorder. Many people in both developed and developing countries deal with mental health concern from time to time and sometimes these mental health concern become mental illness when signs and symptoms become frequent and leads to disability of person (Horwitz 2020).

When mental health become miserable than many problems started in person life such as during job, study or family time. The management of condition needs both psychotherapy and medication for better life and effective health system in community. The signs and symptoms of disease vary from person to person depend on gender, nature of disease and severity. The symptoms of mental illness can also affects the thoughts, feelings and emotions of persons negatively. Some of the symptoms of disease include excessive fear or worries, feeling down or sad, tiredness, inability to cope up with regular problems, problems associated with the use of alcohol, change in eating pattern and suicidal thinking (Vigod and Stewart 2009).

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Figure 1:The prevalence of mental illness is highest in most developed countries such as United State. According to an estimate 1 out of 5 people in U.S are experiencing mental illness due to use of large amount of alcohol in regular use. The people of all countries experienced mental related disorders before the age of 14 years. The problem associated with this disease is that the diagnosis and identification of disease is difficult

and mostly remained a mystery. The general public of under developed countries considered it a problem that should not be talked and should remain in secret(Lesage, Rochette et al. 2015).

Anxiety disorder is most common type of mental disorder and in this situation patient experience anxiety but symptoms are constant and over whelming, thus impact the life of people in negative manner.

Literature Review

Teplin et al. conducted a study in 2010 to determine the effective and most used treatment method for mental illness. In the study, the author also collected the data of patients present in jails and dealing with the disease without any proper treatment method. The study found that most of the people were not taking any kind of treatment in all general public as only one-third portion of pollution was taking treatment in the society. Thus, study confirmed that the cause of being increase prevalence of disease was staying it untreated. According to the study, the most common types of mental disorders that were present in people of community and jail was depression and schizophrenia (DeCarolis and Eisch 2010).

Anthony et al. published a study where different treatment of mental illness that were mostly using for healthy lifestyle. The data was also compared with the treatment techniques of mental disorders recommended in various books. The study found that the treatment of patients is largely depend on the attitude of medical health care because people took intuitive from them including nurses, doctors and psychiatrists. Furthermore, the study also found that personalities of patients is also connected with the treatment efficacy and treatment method because the method of treatment is different on personality basis(DAVIDS 1970).

A study was conducted by Abiodun et al. in which it was found many myths are related with the cause of mental illness which are wrong. The purpose of study was to find the actual cause of disease that can initiate the disease or can also worsen the disease. A cross-sectional survey was conducted and the number of patients that were selected for the study were almost 2078. The author and his team members make a questionnaire and give that questionnaire to the relatives of patients to determine the cause of disease. The results of study showed that misuse of psychiatric treatment and beliefs of people were totally wrong and were not related with the real cause of disease. The study also confirmed that education is also related with this disease as most of the people in society are educated that are dealing with the disease (Adewuya and Makanjuola 2008).

Catherine et al. conducted a study in United Kingdom to find the cause of mental diseases especially depression and anxiety disorders because these disorders are high in people at student level. The purpose of study was to found the attitudes of students toward mental disease. The electronic questionnaire was prepared by authors and was distributed in the students to find the cause, treatment and myth of mental disorders. Independent sample was collected to determine the treatment method related to psychiatric issues. The results showed the most of the students respond to electronic questionnaire because almost 54% students filled the form and participate in study (Chiles, Stefanovics et al. 2017).

A study was conducted by Carrie in 2008 to find the link better gender and mental disorder. The study was to determine the prevalence of disease in both male and female gender and association of gender with the treatment. The study found that 5.4% people of all over the world have been diagnosed with different mental diseases including schizophrenia, bipolar disorder, depression and anxiety problems. The study confirmed that there is high association of mental illness with the education, relationship status and employment. Short form health surveys were conducted to determine the association of gender with mental problem. Thus, it was concluded in the study from survey that females are greatly diagnosed with this disease and mostly keep the disease untreated for almost four years (Teh, Kilbourne et al. 2008).

In last, the study was conducted as well as published by Natalie et al. to find the most common age of mentally ill patients. The patients of all age including children, young and old were taken and data was collected to determine the effect of age on disease. The comparison of different age groups of justification of disease cleared that elder and young people are high victim of mental diseases (Slopen, Watson et al. 2007).

Objective

The study was conducted to determine the prevalence of mental diseases in both gender. Furthermore, the cause and awareness in people was also found in the study.

METHODOLOGY:

STUDY DESIGN:

Cross Sectional Study

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:

Sampling technique.

SAMPLE SIZE:

100

INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Men and Women of ages from 20 to 60 with any mental illness
- People having both professional and un-professional life
- General people belongs to different education level such as graduation, master and Phd level
- People who are taking medication, talk therapy or both for the treatment

EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- People who are not taking any precaution or medication
- Patients with an co-morbidity of any other abnormality
- People below the age of 20

Statistical Tool

SPSS version 19

Chi-square test

ETHICAL CONSIDERATION

- Written informed consent was taken from all the patients.
- All informed and collected data will be kept confidential.
- Data will be saved in personal laptop and hard copies from data will be in locker.
- Participants will remain anonymous throughout the study
- The subject was informed there are no disadvantages or risk on the procedure of study.
- They were also informed that they are free to withdraw at any time during the process of the study

DATA COLLECTION

- Data collection sheets were used to collect the data.
- The data was collected according to the variable of gender, qualification, awareness and age
- The demographic data was collected from all the participants.

DATA ANALYSIS

- Appropriate statistical data analysis technique was used with SPSS version
- Chi-Square test was pragmatic in statistical P-value < 0.05 is analyzed.

RESULTS:**Table 1: Qualification of Patients**

Crosstab			Qualification				Total
			Intermediate	Graduation	masters	PhD	
Age	21-30 years	Count	11	12	4	0	27
		% of Total	11.0%	12.0%	4.0%	.0%	27.0%
	31-40 years	Count	13	16	11	2	42
		% of Total	13.0%	16.0%	11.0%	2.0%	42.0%
	41-50 years	Count	2	8	8	4	22
		% of Total	2.0%	8.0%	8.0%	4.0%	22.0%
	51-60 years	Count	2	5	1	1	9
		% of Total	2.0%	5.0%	1.0%	1.0%	9.0%
Total		Count	28	41	24	7	100
		% of Total	28.0%	41.0%	24.0%	7.0%	100.0%

The table 1 shows the frequency of qualification of mental diseases related people including intermediate, graduation, masters and PhD. 28 people out of 100 patients were studied in intermediate level while only 7 people were in PhD. Furthermore, mostly patients as 41 patients were studied in graduation while 24 were from master level.

Table 2: Professionalism

Crosstab			professional		Total
			Yes	No	
Age	21-30 years	Count	9	18	27
		% of Total	9.0%	18.0%	27.0%
	31-40 years	Count	22	20	42
		% of Total	22.0%	20.0%	42.0%
	41-50 years	Count	11	11	22
		% of Total	11.0%	11.0%	22.0%
	51-60 years	Count	4	5	9
		% of Total	4.0%	5.0%	9.0%
Total		Count	46	54	100
		% of Total	46.0%	54.0%	100.0%

The table 2 shows the frequency of professionalism in patients who were dealing with mental health problems such as results confirmed that 46% patient of anxiety and depression were professionalism which means they were doing job but mostly as 54% patients were no doing any which means people who remain free are at major risk of disease.

Table 3: Awareness of mental health services

Crosstab			awareness of mental health services			Total
			Counseling for addiction issues	Treatment of mood/Anxiety disorders	None	
Age	21-30 years	Count	10	4	13	27
		% of Total	10.0%	4.0%	13.0%	27.0%
	31-40 years	Count	19	9	14	42
		% of Total	19.0%	9.0%	14.0%	42.0%
	41-50 years	Count	8	10	4	22
		% of Total	8.0%	10.0%	4.0%	22.0%
	51-60 years	Count	5	0	4	9
		% of Total	5.0%	.0%	4.0%	9.0%
Total		Count	42	23	35	100
		% of Total	42.0%	23.0%	35.0%	100.0%

The table 3 & figure 2 showed the percentage and frequency of awareness of mental health services of mentally retarded people. The results showed that most of the patients as 42% patients were attending counselling sessions for the getting knowledge about disease and also for dealing effectively with disease. Treatment of mood swings due to disease is also necessary because 23% patients were taking medications for treatment of disease.

Figure 2: Awareness of mental health services
Table 4: Causes of Mental Illness

Crosstab			Causes of mental illnesses					Total
			Domestic issues	Demonical causes	Illiteracy	Drug addiction	Others	
Age	21-30 years	Count	8	11	3	4	1	27
		% of Total	8.0%	11.0%	3.0%	4.0%	1.0%	27.0%
	31-40 years	Count	16	11	6	5	4	42
		% of Total	16.0%	11.0%	6.0%	5.0%	4.0%	42.0%
	41-50 years	Count	6	5	2	3	6	22
		% of Total	6.0%	5.0%	2.0%	3.0%	6.0%	22.0%
	51-60 years	Count	3	2	1	2	1	9
		% of Total	3.0%	2.0%	1.0%	2.0%	1.0%	9.0%
Total		Count	33	29	12	14	12	100
		% of Total	33.0%	29.0%	12.0%	14.0%	12.0%	100.0%

The table 4 & figure 3 showed the percentage as well as frequency for major causes that are increasing the rate of disease in the general population. The results showed that the cause of disease for most of the disease was domestic issue in family that was increasing all types of mental disorders. The 2nd top most cause of disease was demonical cause while only 12% cause of disease was illiteracy. Drug addiction was also cause of mental disorder as drinking of alcohol was high in developed countries, therefore, the prevalence of disease is higher in developed countries.

Figure 3: Causes of Mental Illness
Table 5: Treatment Options

Crosstab			Treatment options					Total
			Faith healers/ magicians	General Physicians	psychiatrist and psychologists	Others	None	
Gender	male	Count	14	11	7	7	3	42
		% of Total	14.0%	11.0%	7.0%	7.0%	3.0%	42.0%
	female	Count	25	7	13	9	4	58
		% of Total	25.0%	7.0%	13.0%	9.0%	4.0%	58.0%
Total		Count	39	18	20	16	7	100
		% of Total	39.0%	18.0%	20.0%	16.0%	7.0%	100.0%

The table 5 & figure 4 showed the frequency of treatment options that were patients taken to live healthy life. The results confirmed that most of the patients were getting treatment from faith healers because mostly people were illiterate thus preferred magicians for the treatment. Only 18% patients were taking treatment from physicians but were getting better results while only 7% people were not taking any treatment. Some of them as 20% patients were contacting with psychologist and psychiatrists for the treatment.

Figure 4: Treatment Options

DISCUSSION:

The results showed that mostly women are victim of diseases because most of the women are diagnosed with depression, bipolar and other mental diseases. The results were similar to a study conducted by Carrie which showed that gender is highly associated with the mental diseases. The results of studies confirmed that females are most diagnosed with the disease. The results showed that mostly young patients who were studied in graduation level were linked with any type of mental disease.

The results of study conducted by Natalie et al. were also similar to this study which showed that young people are highly associated with the disease because they have to deal with various complex situations in short period of time. The results showed that cause of disease is still unclear as cause of disease in most of the patient was domestic issue whose root cause is not known. The study of Catherine et al. showed similar results which showed that there are many myths associated with the mental diseases including bipolar disorder and depression.

The results of study determine that different techniques are used to treat the disease in various areas according to their cultural and religious beliefs. The results were exact similar to a study conducted by Anthony et al. which showed that different psychiatric and medication treatment is used for mentally disturbed people.

CONCLUSION:

Mental health related issues are increasing in the countries both developed and developing due to some domestic and family issues. The studies showed that there are various types of mental problems and all types are severe and are increasing the stress. The most severe disease type is depression that is due to complications of societies and due to increase level of innovation.

The treatment of disease is different for people belongs to various culture and religion. The chances of disease is higher in females because female mostly stay at home and does not work due to which think negative thoughts.

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